

Productivity, Management and Cost-Benefit Analyses of Pigeons in Pet Shop of Bangladesh

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Abstract: In Bangladesh pigeon farming is not now well furnished to everybody. Till now it is neglected due to lack of knowledge and public awareness. Pigeon farming and a pet shop establishment could alleviate our poverty at this moment. We have a lot of manpower who has no exact work. They can easily establish a pigeon or bird shop for income and hobby. Whereas our domestic pigeon will be extant in this nature and accepted by everybody. In Bangladesh the environment is suitable for pigeon rearing, less feeding can be implemented; no odour during its rearing and disease was less remarkable found most of the bird shops mainly in Kushtia and Dinajpur district.

Keywords: pigeon, pet shop, cost-benefit, productivity, management.

Introduction:

Pigeons and doves originated in the same line. Both are normally same and in same family columbidae. Pigeons are domesticated and in dove only *Streptopelia risoria* is domesticated and others are wild. The colour variation of dove is huge on the other hand pigeons are less but now selective breeding its colour are increasing day by day. There are near about 300 breeds of pigeon in the world. Victoria is the major squab producing state in Australia. Squabs are really to fly and release their nest at about 26-30 days of age. Then they weight about 500 g and are ready to market for the table. White Kings are the best squab producer. For maximum production regular fly, dry house and good ventilation is must. Floor nestling should be discouraged as squabs on the floor are prone to cannibalism. Breeding squab should select on liveweight 450-700 g. some useful female breeding life up to 10 years, and male 5 years. To prevent inbreeding always mated high producing females with younger male which is more vigorous. Continuous selection of large bird pair remain always more males than females. Pigeon normally moult and stop breeding in autumn and winter. Pigeons eat more in the colder months and when caring and hatching. 25 breeding pairs will eat about 3 kg of feed daily. Many pigeon breeders separate their pigeon in October and re-mate April and stop October and cooler climates.

Materials and Methods:

Pigeon breeds: During the time of February 2011 to July 2012 in Kushtia and Dinajpur pigeon shop

there were several breeds of pigeons. Viz-Lahore, Fantail, Pouter, Bokhara, Strasser, Frillback, Homer, Capuchine, King etc. Most of the pigeon shops Fancy and Broiler (as fancy) and sports were as foster.

Feed: Daily two times mixed feed supply. This food contains less corn in summer and more corn in winter due to produce its required heat for breeding. Morning 10:00 a.m. and evening 5:30 p.m. was the feeding time and provide each pigeon 30- 40 gram of feed at one time for a pair. After serving this feed with 10-15 minutes rest of the feed were balanced and easily calculated that what amount feed take by two pigeons. During the time of hatching this food were observed 30-33 gram in each pigeon. At the time of pre-laying stage in Kushtia shop food were served two times in a day but in Dinajpur these were three times served. Per kg feed in Dinajpur 34 taka and in Kushtia this is 50 taka. The items were good in Dinajpur with mixed food with broiler food but in Kushtia this is wheat, corn, Japaese millet, sunflower seed and paddy.

Cage and pot measurements: In Kushtia large cages for King and Strasser pigeon was 30x24x20 inches whereas in Dinajpur this is 24x18x16 inches. Pot measurements were ---in Dinajpur and in Kushtia this is 6x3x3 and 5x2.5x3. Rearing style was intensive in both shops.

Cost study: In house rent, electricity and other expenditure by month in Kushtia 6000 taka but in Dinajpur this is 2700 taka only.

Diseases: No diseases were found in Dinajpur but in Kuthtia Newcastle and eye problem were found.

No medicines were used except antiworm and some vitamins.

Calculation: After balance rest of the feed in pots it could be easily found that which amount the pigeons were swallowed. Daily basis feed consumption could easily for a month by using into thirty.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1. 1st six months (February 2011 - October 2011):

Table 2. 2nd six months (November 2011 –July 2012):

Conclusion:

From the very beginning pigeon rearing was just hobby for human and recreation and finally for eating its squab. Now-a-days through our huge manpower and not getting their suitable job so they easily motivated pigeon rearing. Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi, Khulna, Nature, Pabna, Naogaon, Dinajpur, Kushtia and Bheramara and other places this pigeon traditions are good in number. Pigeons' future is very fruitful no doubt in our coming days. Pigeon can be an experimental lab bird as well as its genetics studies. We can easily produce colourful and excellent feathered pigeons through selective breeding. In can be implemented broiler pigeon for the source of protein production. Besides I think pigeons can be second poultry of Bangladesh. Moreover, our environment is much more better than others for pigeon farming. So, it can be surely concluded that pigeon farming on the roof of the residence and in shop in urban areas pigeons showed the development of Bangladesh.

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References:

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